

Research article

Geolinguistic analysis of word forms for ‘today’ in Tibetic languages in Yunnan

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Abstract: This article describes the word forms for ‘today’ in Kham Tibetan varieties spoken in Yunnan, China, and analyses their distribution. It confirms two types of word forms: (1) /tV/ as the first syllable and (2) /ʔa/ as the first syllable. The distribution of (1) is observed in the Sems-kyi-nyila group, while that of (2) is in the other groups. Despite rGyalthang (the Sems-kyi-nyila group) being the governmental, economic, and religious centre, the second form exhibits a higher expansion power.*

Keywords: Tibetic; Kham Tibetan; lexical distribution; expansion; syllabic coalescence

1. Introduction

This article first describes word forms for ‘today’ in Kham Tibetan varieties in the Tibetosphere of Yunnan Province, China, and then examines how they are distributed from a geolinguistic viewpoint. Figure 1 shows the most recent dialectal classification of these varieties (Suzuki 2022c), which is a revised version of Suzuki (2018).

The morphological features of ‘today’ in various languages have been discussed by works such as Iwata (2009, 2021) for Sinitic. However, scholars have not investigated the word form for ‘today’ in Yunnan Tibetan and even in Tibetic languages from a geolinguistic perspective. Its description will provide the first account of day ordinals (cf. Bradley 2007: 138–139; 2013) in Tibetic languages. In addition, I will examine the geolinguistic features of the word form for ‘today’ in Yunnan Tibetan.

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Fig. 1 Classification of Yunnan Tibetan.

2. Word forms

The Literary Tibetan (LT) word for ‘today’ is *de ring* (hypothetical literal meaning: ‘that’ + ‘long’), and the spoken forms in the target varieties are classified into four:

- (1a) a disyllabic form corresponding to the LT form, e.g., /tə rī/ and /tə rēj/;
- (1b) a disyllabic form of which the first initial consonant is /t/, partially differing from the LT form, e.g., /^hteŋ ŋu/ and /tə nu:/;
- (1c) a monosyllabic form of which the initial consonant is /t/, e.g., /tā^s/; and
- (2) a disyllabic form of which the first syllable is /ʔa/, e.g., /ʔa ri:/ and /ʔa rēj/.

Types (1a–c) are related to LT *de ring*, in which (1c) can be derived from either (1a) or (1b). The second syllable of Type (1b) does not correspond to that of the LT form, *ring*, because its initial is a nasal (/n/ or /ŋ/), which is probably related to LT *nub* ‘west,

‘sunset’. This word is used as a part of compounds such as *sang nub* ‘tomorrow evening’ and *kha nub* ‘last night’.

Meanwhile, Type (2) uses /ʔa/ instead of the form corresponding to the LT first syllable *de*. The syllable /ʔa/ is often connected to the vicinal demonstrative, ‘this’, although it does not function as a demonstrative alone. Hence, the hypothetical LT form *a ring* would literally mean ‘this’ + ‘long’.

3. Geographical distribution and its analyses

Figure 2 shows the distribution of the four types mentioned above.

Fig. 2 Word forms for ‘today’.

Comparing this with Figure 1, which reflects the genetic classification based on the shared innovations of the sound change process, we find the broadest distribution of Type (2) whereas Types (1a, b, c) appear in limited varieties of the Sems-kyi-nyila dialect group.

From Figure 2, we can interpret the origins of Types (1b) and (1c), which are only found in the Melung subgroup in the present dataset, as also shown by Daan, a variety belonging to the said subgroup (Suzuki 2009). Suzuki (2022b) proposed a model of Sems-kyi-nyila Tibetan varieties that displays a branching of ‘proto-Melung’ and ‘proto-rGyalthagic’ at an earlier stage. If Suzuki’s (2022b) branching model is accurate, Types (1b) and (1c) substituted Type (1a) after the Melung group separated from other Sems-kyi-nyila Tibetan varieties.

Considering the phonetic realisation of Type (1c), we observe the existence of the pharyngealised feature as in /t̪ʰˤ/. Suzuki (2011) argued that pharyngealisation in the Zhollam variety originated from either the /r/-sound preceding the vowel or coalescence of two syllables. Hence, Type (1c) can originate from either (1a) or (1b) depending on the analysis. Nevertheless, no evidence has demonstrated the Zhollam variety’s independent development in the lexical features within the Melung subgroup. Hence, it is more probable that Type (1c) originates from a coalescence of the disyllabic form of Type (1b).

The word forms of Type (2) are considered recent forms since we find no LT form that corresponds to that type. They appear in all dialectal groups spoken in Yunnan. The centre of Type 2’s distribution is in the north-west area of Figure 2, and the distribution is extended to a geographically contiguous area from the north-west to the south-east, based on the Yunnan Tibetosphere. Figure 3 illustrates a combination pattern of the dialectal classification and the word forms.

As Figure 3 shows, the varieties of the Sems-kyi-nyila group spoken in the connecting zone with the other dialectal groups accepted Type (2). They belong to the East Yunling Mountain, dNgo, and Lamdo subgroups, with the last two exhibiting a degree of commonality in phonological development process with the sDerong-nJol and Chaphreng groups. Hence, it is reasonable that they share lexical features with these non-Sems-kyi-nyila groups.

However, we consider it a striking phenomenon that most East Yunling Mountain subgroup varieties systematically received the lexical item for ‘today’ from another dialect group. From this perspective, the varieties spoken in mBacug Village noticeably use Type (1a) between the distribution areas of Type (2) (Qidzong; East Yunling Mountain subgroup) and Type (1b) (mThachu; Melung subgroup). Based on the phonological shared innovations, the mBacug varieties are classified in the East Yunling Mountain subgroup under the Sems-kyi-nyila group. Hence, we can argue that the word form for ‘today’ *has not been substituted* by Type (2). One factor of such retention may be the location of mBacug, which is on the hill remote to the main traffic route.

Fig. 3 Relation between the classification and the word forms for 'today'.

For the entire Tibetic languages, the Sems-kyi-nyila group is distributed at the south-eastern periphery of the Tibetosphere (Roche and Suzuki 2018; Tournadre and Suzuki 2023); thus, the case of Sems-kyi-nyila seems to be retention of the archaic form following the concentric theory. However, Type (1a) is still used in the central area of the Tibetosphere. Simply put, Type (2) is a local form developed in the region centred on the north-western part of Yunnan, and Figure 3 shows a situation in which Type (2), a newcomer, gradually expands its power beyond the dialect groups.

4. Conclusion

This article examined the lexical forms for ‘today’ in Tibetic languages in the Yunnan Tibetosphere. Two greater forms are observed: (1) derived from LT *de ring* and *de nub* and (2) derived from another form, *a ring*. The distribution of (1) is confirmed in the Sems-kyi-nyila group, while that of (2) is seen in the other groups. However, form (2) gradually expands its power to the periphery of the Sems-kyi-nyila group, substituting form (1). Contrary to the governmental, economic, and religious centre being in rGyalthang (the Sems-kyi-nyila group), form (2) demonstrates more power of expansion.

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